

INFLUENCE OF REACTION ZONE THICKNESS ON TENSILE STRENGTH FOR
TITANIUM-MATRIX COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH SiC FIBER

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we have been investigated on influence of reaction zone on tensile strength of SiC fiber(CVD) reinforced composites with various Ti matrix. It was observed that the reaction zone in titanium-matrix composites reinforced with SiC fiber was mainly composed of TiC and Ti_5Si_3 . In growth rate of reaction zone, Ti-21V-4Al matrix appeared to be lower than those of CPTi and Ti-6Al-4V matrices. It was because large amounts of alloying elements of vanadium and aluminum reduced the growth rate of the reaction zone. In this case of CPTi and Ti-6Al-4V matrices the apparent activation energy for the growth rate of the reaction zone revealed that the value of the activation energy was different between the heating temperatures above and below the alpha-beta transformation or beta transus temperature because of rapid diffusion rate and low solubility of carbon in beta phase. The tensile strength of these composites was lineally decreased with the increase of the reaction zone, whereas tensile strength was not reduced up to about $1\mu m$ thickness of the reaction zone. The fracture mechanism of the reaction zone could be explained by the use of the circumferential notch theory proposed by Irwin. Such elements as vanadium, aluminum, chromium and molybdenum up to about 30 atomic percent, and zirconium and tin up to about 10 atomic percent in Ti-base binary matrix composites play the most important role for the decrease of the growth rate of the reaction zone. From these results, it was found that the above additives were effective for interfacial reaction in SiC/Ti matrix composites.

Key Words : Composites, Titanium Alloy, SiC-CVD Fiber, Activation Energy, Reaction Zone, Growth Rate, Fracture mechanism, Ti-base binary alloy

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, FRM(Fiber Reinforced Metals) occupy the attention as the most promising emerging materials. As most artificial FRM are consolidated in a thermodynamically non-equilibrium state and are thermal exposed at elevated temperature. Interfacial chemical reaction between fiber and matrix often takes place. The interfacial reaction has been known as one of the cause in degrading mechanical properties of composites[1-5]. Recently, much research has been done on the fiber-matrix reaction in titanium-matrix composites. There are only a few reports to explain identification and growth mechanism of reaction products in interface using X-ray diffraction and energy dispersed microanalyses(EPMA). However, the study on the titanium-matrix composites has not been fully carried out.

In this paper, we are going to investigated from the view point of physic chemistry on interfacial reaction of titanium and titanium alloy matrix composites reinforced with silicon carbide(SiC), using transmission electron microscopy(TEM), SEM/EDX and EPMA. From the results obtained, the degradation mechanism of titanium and titanium alloy matrix composites system is also evaluated as a function of the thickness of reaction zone. And the effects of various kinds of alloying elements on the growth rate of reaction zone were also examined using Ti-base binary alloys matrices.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials Two types of silicon carbide fibers were used in this study. One, referred to as the SiC(W) fiber, is beta silicon carbide with a nominal diameter of $100\mu\text{m}$. The other is SCS-6 type SiC fiber($140\mu\text{m}$) produced by AVCO, by means of chemical vapour deposition[6].

Three kinds of matrix foils with a thickness of $100\mu\text{m}$ were used : commercially pure titanium(CPTi), Ti-6Al-4V and Ti-21V-4Al alloy. The CPTi is an alpha alloy with the alpha-beta transformation at 1153K. The Ti-6Al-4V alloy is an alpha/beta alloy with the alpha-beta transus at 1268K. The Ti-21V-4Al alloy is a beta alloy. The tensile strength of these matrix are 500MPa, 900MPa and 700MPa, respectively.

Ti-base binary alloys contained 2-30 atomic percent of aluminum, nickel, vanadium, molybdenum, zirconium, tin and chromium were prepared for the purpose of examining the interfacial reaction rate for SiC fiber.

2.2 Fabrication process of FRM FRM were prepared by hot-press at 1123K and under high vacuum of $1 \times 10^{-2}\text{Pa}$ under condition as shown Figure 1. The organic fugitive binder was carefully baked off at 773K under vacuum before

temperature and uniaxial pressure was raised to 1123K and 70 to 90 MPa, respectively, for 100h.

2.3 Thermal exposure and microstructure The FRM (50mm x 60mm x 1.4mm ; 8 to 10 fiber layers ; $V_f=0.31$ to 0.37) were then cut, paralleled to the fiber direction and then set inside silica glass tubes and sealed under high vacuum. They were thermal exposed at temperature ranging from 1073 to 1373K for duration up to 360ks, and then carefully polished and etched cross section. Observation for the reaction zone thickness was carried out by SEM. Because of the uneven nature of the reaction zone, the average value for 20 measurements of the reaction zone thickness was used. TEM thin-foil specimens were prepared from 70 μ m by mechanical grinding. And then, the disk was thinned to electron transparency with a ion milling apparatus. It typically takes 50h in the ion miller operating at 5KV and 0.5mA.

Ti-base binary alloy prepared for the purpose of examining on the reaction rate of SCS-6 fiber and titanium-matrix were fabricated FRM with the SCS-6 fiber at 1173K, 90MPa for 100h. The thermal-exposed Ti-base binary alloy FRM at 1173K for 72h were calculated the reaction rate by measurements the thickness of reaction zone using SEM/EDX.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure The SiC fiber/Ti matrix interface in cross section of the as-fabricated and thermal-exposed specimens are shown in Figure 2. Figure 2(a) is illustrated as-fabricated SCS-6/Ti-21V-4Al FRM. The reaction zone appears to be about 0.5 μ m. The black parts of fiber sides of reaction zone show the outer surface of fiber that have a non-stoichiometric, carbon-rich mixture of carbon and silicon. Figure 2(b) is illustrated reaction zone thermal-exposed SiC(W)/CPTi FRM at 1173K for 72h. The reaction zone appears to be about 9 μ m.

Figure 2(c) is illustrated reaction zone annealed SiC(W)/Ti-6Al-4V FRM at 1123K for 12h. The reaction zone grows at the expense of both the titanium matrix and the fiber surface layer, with latter being consumed, in a non-uniform manner, resulting in an undulated surface. At those place where the fiber contacts beta phase in the titanium matrix, the reaction zone consumes the fiber surface layer and grow more rapidly than where the fiber contacts alpha phase. Because the high diffusion rate and the lower solubility of carbon in beta phase of titanium matrix, reaction zone grows to more in the beta phase than in the alpha phase[7].

3.2 Identification of reaction products by TEM

Figure 3 reveals TEM

image of a reaction zone between fiber and matrix of SiC(W)/CPTi FRM thermal-exposed at 1273K for 4h. From microdiffraction of TEM image, it was observed the reaction zone consisted of three layers of the narrow ($\sim 0.2\mu\text{m}$) layer adjacent to the fiber, the narrow ($\sim 0.2\mu\text{m}$) layer adjacent to the matrix and the intermediate layer. Microdiffraction of the three layers is revealed in Figure 4.

From Figure 4, the outermost layer where adjacent to the matrix was found to be Ti_5Si_3 (a), and the crystallographic orientation in the interface of Ti_5Si_3 intermetallic compounds and alpha titanium matrix was found to be $(211)_{\text{Ti}_5\text{Si}_3} // (110)_{\text{Ti}}$. Whereas, the innermost layer where adjacent to the fiber was found to be a mixture of TiC (b), TiSi_2 (c) and Ti_5Si_3 , and the intermediate layer was a mixture of TiC and Ti_5Si_3 . However, TiSi_2 was not identified in the intermediate layer. Hence, the reaction zone are considered to be a mixture of TiC and Ti_5Si_3 .

3.3 Kinetics of reaction zone

Figure 5 is shown the relation between the reaction zone thickness and thermal exposure time in fiber-matrix interface of specimens exposed at (a)1173K and (b)1223K. The average reaction zone thickness, x , increase linearly with the square root of the exposure time, t , at a given temperature, at least in a first approximation and if the reaction zone is not too thick:

$$x = kt^{1/2} \quad (k : \text{reaction rate constants}) \quad (1)$$

At a given temperature, the growth rate of the reaction zone is lower for the Ti-21V-4Al matrix than for CPTi. Both the Ti-6Al-4V and Ti-21V-4Al matrix contain aluminum and vanadium. Aluminum which does not seem to be present in the reaction zone, whereas vanadium is present in small amounts in the zone, could play the most important role for the reaction rate decrease. Because those elements appeared to be rejected in front of the reaction zone, those elements are considered to diffusion control due to diffuse rate into the matrix .

The thermal variations of k follow an arrhenius law in the 1073 to 1373K temperature range,

$$k = k_0 \exp(-Q/2RT) \quad (2)$$

where k_0 and Q (the apparent activation energy for formation: kJ/mol) are material constants, T is the absolute temperature and R is the gas constants ($R=8.3144\text{J/K}$), as shown in Figure 6. The apparent activation energy for the growth rate of the reaction zone revealed that the value of the activation

energy was different between the heating temperature above and below the alpha-beta transformation or beta transus temperature in case of CPTi and Ti-6Al-4V alloy matrices because of rapid diffusion rate and low solubility of carbon in beta phase. The values of k_0 and Q are given in Table 1.

3.4 Correlation between tensile strength and the reaction zone thickness

The relation between thermal exposure time and tensile strength of the composites were illustrated in Figure 7. Comparising with the theoretical strength of composites by the rule of mixture of composites, the tensile strength of as-fabricated composites are obtained about 86-96%. This may be due to the defects occurred during fabrication and composites failure by the fracture of the weakest fiber. The tensile strength of SCS-6/CPTi FRM is lowered with the thermal exposure time, but the tensile strength of SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V FRM and SCS-6/Ti-21V-4Al FRM did not lower up to 6hr, 12hr, respectively, and then the tensile strength are lowered with the thermal exposure time. The degradation of the tensile strength with the thermal exposure time is considered as increase of reaction zone thickness by the interaction of fiber-matrix.

Figure 8 is presented on the tensile strength of these composites with various thickness of the reaction zone, and also thermal-exposed the strength, σ_c^* , with respect to the strength before thermal exposure, σ_c . It was considered that these composites had strong interface, because if debonding had occurred, the reduction in composite strength showed in Figure 7 should not have taken place. The tensile strength of these thermal-exposed composites are not lowered when the thickness of reaction zone is less than $1\mu\text{m}$. This fact enables us to predict the permissible thickness of the reaction zone for various fiber materials.

The σ_c^*/σ_c is plotted versus thermal exposure time t in Figure 9. From Figure 7, SCS-6/CPTi FRM reaction zone grows fastest to $1\mu\text{m}$ thickness, Ti-6Al-4V FRM grows second fastest, and Ti-21V-4Al FRM, latest. It is considered that the growth rate of reaction zone in Ti-21V-4Al matrix was lower than those in CPTi and Ti-6Al-4V matrix, because alloying elements of vanadium and aluminum reduced the growth rate of reaction zone.

Tensile strength of FRM depends largely on strength of fiber. However, if brittle reaction zone be interface of fiber-matrix, the tensile strength was dependent upon behavior of brittle interface layers. That is, fracture mechanism is determined by crack propagation for a formation of a notch. When the brittle zone fractures and a notch is formed in an early stage of deformation, the composite is able to be regarded as a rod with a circumferential notch.

The fiber strength σ_f^* for a rod with a circumferential notch is given by

Irwin[5]

$$\sigma_f^* = (1/1.1)(E_f G_c^* / \pi c)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where E_f is the Young's modulus of the fiber, G_c^* is the critical strain energy release rate of the fiber, and c is the brittle zone thickness. From Equation 3, the tensile strength of fiber is known as a function of brittle zone thickness. As the Young's modulus of a fiber was resulted in 440MPa, the critical strain energy release rate of the fiber G_c^* obtained 94.08 J/m² into Equation 3 the value.

The fracture toughness K_C for a rod with a circumferential notch, for plane stress is given by Irwin[8]

$$K_C = (G_c^* E_f)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

In the calculation, the fracture toughness K_C was obtained 6.43 MPa m^{1/2}.

3.5 Effects of additives on reaction rate

Figure 10 shows the effect of different types of additives on the reaction rate constant at 1173k. The effect of additives in titanium on the reaction rate to provide the necessary background data for development of alloys compatible with SiC fiber and Ti-base binary alloys. The influence of additives in titanium on the reaction rate of reaction zone may be divided into three type. Where, the reaction rate constant in titanium at 1173K showed $1.71 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm/sec}^{1/2}$ from Figure 6. Nickel is representative of the first type which acts as a accelerator that the concentration of the titanium is increased abruptly to the amount of element in the solid solution. Zirconium and tin cause a fast rate constitute the second type of alloying element behavior, but these elements of above 10 at% increases abruptly to the amount of element in the solid solution. Vanadium, aluminum, molybdenum and chromium represent the third type which acts as a dilute that the effective concentration of the titanium is reduced slowly to the amount of element in solid solution.

In case of added nickel and above about 10 at% zirconium and tin, the increase of reaction rate is considered as nucleation and growth of carbide and silicide by interaction for element in titanium with SiC fiber and growth of Ti_5Si_3 and TiC by reaction of titanium matrix-SiC fiber. On the other hands, the decrease of reaction rate with the additive of vanadium, aluminum, molybdenum and chromium elements and below about 10 at% zirconium and tin would be expected from considerations of elements such as free energy of formation and phase stability and rate-determining for rejection of these elements from the reaction zone to matrix.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The strength of titanium-matrix composites were measured by fracture of tensile strength, and the identification and the growth rate of reaction zone were investigated by SEM and TEM. The main results are as follows.

- 1) The major reaction products are TiC and Ti_5Si_3 because of thermodynamical stabilization and concentration gradient by diffusion.
- 2) It is found that the growth rate of reaction zone in Ti-21V-4Al alloy matrix was lower than those in CPTi and Ti-6Al-4V alloy matrices, because alloying elements of vanadium and aluminum are considered to diffusion control of carbon from fiber.
- 3) The values of the apparent activation energy are different between the heating temperatures above and below the transformation or transus temperature in case of CPTi and Ti-6Al-4V matrices. This phenomenon is due to the high diffusivity and low solubility of carbon in beta phase.
- 4) The tensile strength of these composites decrease with increasing of the reaction zone, but the strength was not reduced when the thickness of reaction zone was up to about $1\mu m$. Finally, the thickness of reaction zone must be controlled less than $1\mu m$.
- 5) The Ti-base binary alloys matrix composites containing vanadium, aluminum, chromium and molybdenum up to about 30 at%, and zirconium and tin up to about 10 at% decrease the growth rate of the reaction zone with the increase of the additives. However, the additive of nickel and above 10 at% zirconium and tin are required for attention the additive of these elements because of the increase of reaction rate.

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Figure 1 Fabrication process

Figure 3 TEM images of a reaction zone between SiC fiber and CPTi matrix

Figure 2 SEM images of fiber/matrix interface (a)SCS-6/Ti-21V-4Al(as-fabricated state), (b)SiC(W)/CPTi(thermal-exposed state; 1173K, 72h), (c)SiC(W)/Ti-6Al-4V (thermal-exposed state; 1223K, 4h)

Figure 4 reaction zone layer identified by microdiffraction ; (a) Ti and Ti_5Si_3 , (b) TiC, (c) $TiSi_2$

Figure 5 Curves of $x^2=f(t)$ for composites thermal-exposed at (a) 1173K and (b) 1223K

Figure 6 $\ln k=f(1/T)$ arrhenius plots for composites thermal-exposed at temperature ranging from 1073 to 1373K

Table 1 Values of Q (apparent of activation energy for formation : kJ/mol) and k_0 (constants: $\times 10^{-2}$ cm/sec^{1/2})

Composites	SiC(w)/CPTi		SiC(w)/Ti-6Al-4V		SCS-6/CPTi		SCS-6/Ti-6Al-4V		SCS-6/Ti-21V-4Al
	below	above	below	above	below	above	below	above	
Q	90	110	93	120	81	85	95	118	77
k_0	2.00	13.50	2.90	23.60	0.69	1.01	1.81	15.70	0.26

Figure 7 Relation between tensile strength and thermal-exposed time for composites

Figure 8 Variation of σ_c^*/σ_c as a function of reaction zone thickness c of composites

Figure 9 Variation of σ_c^*/σ_c as a function of thermal-exposed time t of composites

Figure 10 Effects of alloying elements on reaction rate constants for silicon carbide-titanium reaction